

HEART ARRHYTHMIAS

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Abstract: Currently, the study of cardiac arrhythmias is very important, because they are common among respiratory system diseases and can cause life-threatening complications for the patient. It also causes damage to internal organs that are important for life.

Key words: arrhythmia, excitability, conduction and contractility

Arrhythmias are disorders of the heart rhythm. Arrhythmias are caused by disturbances in the basic functions of the heart, automatism, excitability, conduction and contractility.

Arrhythmias have different causes. Patients may not notice some of them, but due to the second type of arrhythmias, patients may lose their jobs. Therefore, knowing arrhythmias is of great importance for us.

Reasons. The causes of heart rhythm disorders are considered to be the following.

-Organic diseases of the heart (IUD, rheumatism, myocarditis, cardiomyopathy, heart disease, hypertension, etc.).

-Functional diseases (vegetative nervous system lability).

-Physical and chemical effects (under the influence of excess body fat, alcohol, digitalis, sympathomimetics and diuretics).

-Idiopathic heart rhythm disorder.

Normally, impulses for heart contractions are released from the sinus node. The sinus node is considered a 1st order rhythm driver. Normally, 60-90 impulses are released from the sinus node in 1 minute. Impulses from the sinus node are transmitted to the bundles of Bachmann, Wenkebach, Torrel fibers and the atrioventricular (AV) node. Impulses from the AV node are transmitted to

Purkinje fibers and myocardial muscles through the bundle of His. The AV junction is a rhythm driver of the 2nd order and produces 40-60 impulses in 1 minute. The lower parts of the bundle of His and the Purkinje fibers are considered to be rhythm drivers of the 3rd order and produce up to 20-40 impulses in 1 minute.

Cardiac impulses usually occur as a result of impulses from the sinus node. Because the sinus node normally weakens the automaticity of rhythm drivers located below it. In the case of damage to the sinus node, the function of the rhythm driver can be taken by the automaticity centers of the II and III orders located below.

Ventricular extrasystole. In ventricular extrasystole, the ectopic cell is located on the walls of one of the ventricles. If the ectopic cell is located in the first ventricle, it first occurs in this ventricle, and then with a little delay in the second ventricle. Therefore, the QRS complex is deformed in ventricular extrasystole and its duration can exceed 0.12 seconds. Impulses from the ectopic plane do not reach the bundles due to the fact that the AV node does not transmit the impulses upwards, that is, to the bundles. The pulses are observed as impulses from the sinus node, but the R wave is not detected on the ECG because the R wave is compressed by the deformed ventricular complex. Segment S - T and the T notch is opposite (discordant) to the main notch of the extrasystolic complex. That is, if the main tooth of the extrasystolic complex is characteristic of the R tooth, the S-T segment is below the isoline and the T tooth is negative. If the main notch of the extrasystolic complex is characterized by the S notch, the S-T segment is above the isoline and the T notch is positive. During ventricular extrasystole, there is a compensatory pause.

5 different ECG changes are observed during ventricular extrasystole.

The appearance of an out-of-sequence QRS complex.

The QRS complex is deformed and the duration is longer than 0.12 seconds.

Segment S - T and T teeth are opposite (discordant) direction of the extrasystolic complex to the main tooth.

Absence of R wave before ventricular extrasystole.

Total compensatory pause after ventricular extrasystole.

Paroxysmal tachycardia of the atrioventricular junction. In paroxysmal tachycardia of the atrioventricular junction, the ectopic cell comes out of the atrioventricular junction and the impulses are directed to both the bundles and the ventricles at the same time.

If the ectopic plane is located in the upper parts of the AV junction, the impulses go retrograde and reach the ventricles first, and then the ventricles. That is why the R-Q interval is reduced in the ECG, and a negative R wave is located in front of the QRS complex. Since the impulses go in the direction of the ventricles, the shape of the QRS complex does not change from that of the sinus rhythm.

If the ectopic plane is located in the upper parts of the AV junction, the impulses reach the ventricles and ventricles at the same time. In the ECG, the R wave is not detected because the R wave is compressed with the QRS complex. Since the impulses go in the direction of the ventricles, the shape of the QRS complex does not change from that of the sinus rhythm. If the ectopic plane is located in the lower parts of the AV junction, the impulses first reach the ventricles, and then retrograde to the ventricles. That is why there is a negative R wave after the QRS complex on the EKG. Since the impulses go in the direction of the ventricles, the shape of the QRS complex does not change from that of the sinus rhythm. ECG signs in paroxysmal tachycardia of the atrioventricular junction. A sudden increase in heart rate up to 140-250 beats per minute and a sudden stop of the attack if the correct rhythm is maintained. R wave is negative before or after the QRS complex, or the R wave is not detected on the ECG due to the overlap with the QRS complex. Similarity of the shape of the QRS complex to the shape of the QRS complex before the attack of paroxysmal tachycardia. When the attack of paroxysmal tachycardia stops, a compensatory pause is observed.

Paroxysmal ventricular tachycardia. In paroxysmal tachycardia, the ventricles are located in the walls of one of the ectopic three ventricles. If the ectopic cell is located in the first ventricle, it first occurs in this ventricle, and then with a little delay in the second ventricle. Therefore, in paroxysmal tachycardia of the ventricles, the QRS complex is deformed and its duration can exceed 0.12 seconds. Due to the fact that the AV node does not transmit the impulses up, that is, to the bundles, the impulses from the ectopic node do not reach the bundles, that is, the bundles are reflected as the impulses from the sinus node, but because the R wave is compressed by the deformed ventricular complex, the R wave on the ECG the ablation is delayed, and the ventricles appear as impulses coming out of the ectopic cell (atrioventricular dissociation). Segment S – T and T dentate ventricles are oriented opposite (discordant) to the main dentate of the complex. That is, if the ventricles are the main tooth of the complex, the S-T segment is below the isoline and the T tooth is negative. If the ventricles are the main tooth of the complex, the S-T segment is above the isoline and the T tooth

is positive. An attack of paroxysmal ventricular tachycardia ends with a complete compensatory pause.

Differentiation of parts. Muscle spasms are the contractions of different muscle groups in the muscles 350-700 times per minute. In the multiplicity of the bundles, instead of the entire contraction and contraction of the bundles, there is a chaotic contraction and contraction of the individual groups of muscles. In bundle branching, the AV node does not have the ability to transmit all the impulses coming from the bundles, because most of the impulses reach the refractory state of the AV node. The number of contractions of ventricles is observed up to 150-200 times per minute and varies between R-R. Due to the absence of complete contraction of the bundles, many arrhythmic waves are observed on the ECG instead of the R wave. In the ECG, there is a change in the amplitude of waves, large and small waves.

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